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Scuola Universitaria Superiore Pavia

PhD SDC

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
AND CLIMATE CHANGE

Italian National Agency for New Technologies,
Energy and Sustainable Economic Development

Impact of the Ocean-Atmosphere coupling on extratropical cyclones around the Mediterranean basin

Marco Chericoni, PhD Candidate - IUSS Pavia

Alessandro Anav - ENEA, Italy

Giorgia Fosser - IUSS Pavia, Italy

Emmanouil Flaounas - HCMR, Greece

CA19109 – MEDCYCLONES: European network for Mediterranean cyclones in weather and climate

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Objective

Investigate the added values of the ocean-atmosphere coupling in reproducing the climatology of the Mediterranean cyclones. The analysis will focus on how the use of coupled simulations has to offer a better and deeper understanding of dynamical processes of intense Mediterranean cyclones.

Simulations

- 2 Hindcast simulations** driven by ERA5 (1980 – 2014): **ENEA-REG** regional Earth system model
1. **Standalone:** WRF model with prescribed ERA5 Sea Surface Temperature.
 2. **Coupled:** WRF model coupled with the MITgcm ocean model

Methods

- The simulations are compared with ERA5 reanalysis. The RCM outputs have been upscaled to the ERA5 grid resolution.
- **Storm track method** based on mean sea-level pressure (MSLP), (CycloTRACK, Flaounas et al., 2014).

Analysis

1. **Cyclone climatology:** seasonal distribution, spatial distribution and statistics of most intense Mediterranean cyclones.
2. **Cyclone associated precipitation** and **evaporation** and their sensitivity to air-sea feedbacks and SST differences in Winter season.

Cyclone climatology: 500 most intense Med-cyclones

Seasonal distribution

Statistics

- The cyclones are similarly reproduced between RCMs and ERA5 in terms of both spatio-temporal variability and statistics.
- Most intense cyclones occur mainly during winter and over the Mediterranean Sea.

Spatial distribution

Cyclone associated precipitation and evaporation – Winter season

- We define a **circular disk** with a radius of a constant length, **500km**, around the minimum MSLP track point.
- 500 most intense cyclones, in terms of minimum MSLP, that present 33% of the tracking points in the Mediterranean Sea.
- We select the **same intense cyclones** between ERA5 and the RCMs, **285** out of 500 cyclones.

ERA5 Total distribution

total precipitation differences

total evaporation differences

mean SST differences

Cyclone associated precipitation and evaporation – Winter season

ERA5 Total distribution

mean SST differences

Coupled - Standalone ; $\Delta=0.42$

SST differences: The coupled model present a higher SST mostly over the entire Mediterranean Sea, except for the north part of the Adriatic Sea.

Cyclone associated precipitation and evaporation – Winter season

total precipitation differences

Coupled - Standalone ; $\Delta=0.35$

total evaporation differences

Coupled - Standalone ; $\Delta=1.01$

Ionian Sea:

The higher evaporation and precipitation in the coupled simulation is promoted by the higher SST.

1° main finding

Cyclone associated precipitation and evaporation – Winter season

total precipitation differences

Coupled - Standalone ; $\Delta=0.35$

total evaporation differences

Coupled - Standalone ; $\Delta=1.01$

Tyrrhenian and Adriatic Sea:

- Coupled model: lower evaporation over the sea and lower precipitation over the central part of Italy and north part of the Adriatic Sea.
- The high number of cyclone in this region have an impact on surface heat and moisture loss in the coupled model.

2° main finding

2 main findings:

1. Both precipitation and evaporation are affected in correlation with the rapid SST changes during the development of the cyclones.
2. The effects of the surface heat and moisture loss caused by the cyclones is visible in the Tyrrhenian Sea, where the intense cyclones are more frequent.

Next steps:

- Deeper analysis of the evaporation and precipitation fields, focuses on RCM differences at original (12km) resolution and add Latent and sensible heat fluxes analysis.
- Select the cyclones where the diabatic processes are dominant (strong convection), using the Potential Vorticity framework.

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Thank you for your attention!